

Preparation and Characterization of Barium Strontium Titanate Powder

Htet Htet Nwe¹, Than Than Win² and Yin Maung Maung²

Abstract

Strontium (3 mol%) modified barium titanate (Ba(Sr)TiO₃)(BST) crystalline powder was firstly prepared by solid-state mixed oxide route. Ball-milling was also performed to get average particle sized powder. Three-step mesh (100 mesh, 250 mesh, 400 mesh) was used to obtain uniform grain size of Ba(Sr)TiO₃ powder. X-ray Diffraction (XRD) technique was used to know structural properties of BST powder. The decomposition and crystalline behavior of BST were examined by Thermogravimetric and Simultaneous Differential Thermal Analysis (TG-DTA). Energy Dispersive X-ray Fluorescent (EDXRF) technique was employed to examine the quantitative analysis of BST specimen. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) investigation was performed to examine grain size and microstructural properties of BST powder after sieving with mesh and compared to that of BST powder before sieving.

Key words: BST powder, XRD, TG-DTA, EDXRF, SEM

Introduction

Perovskite is a family name of a group of materials and the mineral name of calcium titanate (CaTiO₃) having a structure of the type ABO₃. Many piezoelectric, including ferroelectric, ceramics such as lead titanate (PbTiO₃), barium titanate (BaTiO₃) etc this kind of material has perovskite structure with general formula ABO₃. The solid state reaction method is the traditional method for preparing BaTiO₃ powders by mixing the starting materials, usually titanium dioxide and barium carbonate and calcinations them at an elevated temperature around 1200°C. However, the solid-state reaction method tends to result in a significant amount of agglomeration, poor chemical homogeneity and undesirable secondary phase such as BaTi₂O₅ (Htet Htet Nwe et al, 2010).

Barium oxide is a white hygroscopic compound formed by the burning of barium in oxygen, although it is often formed through the decomposition of other barium salts. Barium oxide is used as a coating for hot cathodes, and in cathode ray tubes. Barium oxide also has used as an ethoxylation catalyst in the reaction of ethylene oxide and alcohols, which takes place between 150 and 200°C [website 1]. Strontium oxide or strontia, SrO, is formed when strontium reacts with oxygen. It is a strongly basic oxide. Strontium is a grey, silvery metal that is softer than calcium and even more reactive in water, with which it reacts on contact to produce strontium hydroxide and hydrogen gas (Goresy et al, 2001).

Titanium dioxide occurs in nature as well-known minerals rutile, anatase and brookite, and additionally as two high pressure forms, a monoclinic baddeleyite-like form and an orthorhombic α -PbO₂-like form. The most common form is rutile, which is also the most stable form. Anatase and brookite both convert to rutile upon heating. Rutile, anatase and brookite all contain six coordinated titanium. Titanium dioxide is found in almost every sunscreen with a physical blocker because of its high refractive index, its strong UV light absorbing capabilities and its resistance to discolouration under ultraviolet light (Lance et al, 2000). Barium titanate is one of most important ceramics due to its outstanding dielectric and ferroelectric properties in the applications of multilayer capacitors, thermistors and electric devices. The performance of barium titanate ceramics significantly depends on the microstructure and sintered body, much attention has been made to the control of powder synthesis, which produces well-crystallized particles with suitable size, distribution and morphology (Xing et al, 2004). Barium titanate is a high-dielectric-constant material and is widely used in the manufacture of multilayer ceramic capacitors (MLCC) (Ahmad et al, 2005). Barium strontium titanate (BST), a solid solution

¹Dr., Demonstrator, Department of Physics, Dagon University

²Dr., Lecturer, Department of Physics, University of Yangon

perovskite, is a potential candidate for integration into microwave devices. BST ferroelectric thin films are attractive for radio frequency and microwave applications due to its high figure of merit, thermal stability and ease of integration into microelectronic circuit (Htet Htet Nwe et al, 2012).

Growth of Ba(Sr)TiO₃ Powder

Barium carbonate (BaCO₃), titanium dioxide (TiO₂) and strontium carbonate (SrCO₃) were mixed by solid state mixed oxide route. This powder was mixed by using agate mortar and calcined at 1200 °C for 1 h and 30 min in order to decarbonate. BST crystalline powder was sieved with 3-step mesh sieve (100 mesh, 250 mesh, 400 mesh) to get uniform grain/particle size. This powder was operated by ball mill to reduce particle size. As a result, the homogeneous and moisture-less crystalline BST powder was formed at a given temperature. The flow diagram of preparation of BST powder was indicated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Flow diagram of Ba(Sr)TiO₃ powder preparation

XRD Analysis of BST Powder

The XRD pattern of Ba(Sr)TiO₃ powder was shown in Figure 2. The reference XRD profile was # 89-0274 barium strontium titanium oxide (Ba_{0.67}Sr_{0.33})(TiO₃) JCPDS file. The sample was scanned over the range 10° to 70° at a scan rate of 1°/min. The obtained XRD pattern was analyzed by using PROSZKI software package and the diffraction peaks were indexed. On the pattern, lower side of the pattern showed the standard or reference XRD pattern and upper side of the profile showed the observed peak. On the Figure, there were 7 standard reflections and 7 observed reflections. It was found that standard reflections were perfect matched with observed reflections and it showed that strontium was absolutely occupied by barium titanate. The most dominant peak was (110) reflection and the corresponding Bragg's angles were 22.282°, 31.7°, 39.06°, 45.478°, 51.159°, 56.659° and 66.258° respectively.

As the detailed analysis, most of the peaks were formed with left-shifted to the standard reflections. The most dominant peak was formed with unidentified co-existing peak and it might be due to the formation of secondary phase such as BaTi_2O_5 . The unnecessary peaks were appeared and it was due to impurities during annealing period. As a result, $\text{Ba}(\text{Sr})\text{TiO}_3$ was absolutely formed at a given temperature.

TGA-DTA Analysis

Figure 3 indicated the TG-DTA peak of BST specimen. From the graph, it was observed that the endothermic and exothermic peaks were formed. The exo peak was occurred at 450°C while the endo peak was found at 100°C and 150°C . As it was seen in Figure, it was obvious that oscillatory behaviour was significantly observed. There were two further different states in the thermal composition process. The final weight loss was being completed at about 450°C . Thus the exothermic DTA peaks were associated with the TGA weight loss and were indicative at organic combustion steps. The exo peak was also formed at about 450°C and it might be associated with the BST crystalline process. The combined TGA and DTA data indicated that slow heating resulted in transformation of the colloidal solution to crystalline BST at about 450°C .

Figure 2. XRD pattern of BST specimen

Figure 3. TG-DTA peak of BST specimen

Elemental Analysis of $\text{Ba}(\text{Sr})\text{TiO}_3$ by EDXRF Technique

Energy Dispersive X-ray Fluorescent (EDXRF) technique was employed to examine the quantitative analysis of $\text{Ba}(\text{Sr})\text{TiO}_3$ specimen. Figure 4 showed the XRF spectrum of $\text{Ba}(\text{Sr})\text{TiO}_3$ specimen. From the spectrum, it was found that the most intense peak was Ba element. Table 1 described the quantitative results of elemental composition for $\text{Ba}(\text{Sr})\text{TiO}_3$ specimen. According to the elemental analysis, the exact composition of Ba, Sr and Ti were obtained. The XRF results were found to be well-matched with those of stoichiometric formula.

Table 1. Element Composition of $\text{Ba}(\text{Sr})\text{TiO}_3$ specimen

Element	Ba	Sr	Ti	Fe
Composition(%)	54.228	27.240	17.971	0.560

SEM Analysis of BST Powder

Two types of $\text{Ba}(\text{Sr})\text{TiO}_3$ powder (before and after mesh-sieving) were analyzed by SEM technique. The observed SEM photographs of $\text{Ba}(\text{Sr})\text{TiO}_3$ powder were described at Figure 5.

Crack-free and fine grains were clearly observed on both SEM microphotographs. The grain sizes were estimated to be $1.7\mu\text{m}$ and $1.53\mu\text{m}$ for $\text{Ba}(\text{Sr})\text{TiO}_3$ powder without and with three-stage mesh. Both microstructures were oriented toward left side and non-uniform grain distribution. Some pores and grain growth pattern were formed among the crystalline grains.

Figure 4. XRF spectrum of BST specimen

Figure 5. SEM microphotograph of BST powder (a) before mesh-sieving, (b) after mesh-sieving

Conclusion

Fabrication and characterization of $\text{Ba}(\text{Sr})\text{TiO}_3$ specimen have been successfully investigated. From XRD result, it was found that the modifier, Sr was totally occupied by Ba-site (A-site). From the XRD result of $\text{Ba}(\text{Sr})\text{TiO}_3$ powder, it was found that strontium (ionic radius of $\text{Sr}^{2+} = 0.127 \text{ nm}$) was tended to enter into Ba-site (A-site) (ionic radius of $\text{Ba}^{2+} = 0.143 \text{ nm}$). Thus the elevated temperature was quite suitable to form $\text{Ba}(\text{Sr})\text{TiO}_3$ powder. In addition, it was also known that the observed $\text{Ba}(\text{Sr})\text{TiO}_3$ had polycrystalline nature.

From TG-DTA analysis, the exothermic peak was found at about 450°C and the final weight loss was being completed at this temperature. From XRF result, it was obvious that the exact composition was formed and consistent with the result of stoichiometric formula. This fact indicated the purification of BST and it was confirmed that this specimen was Ba(Sr)TiO₃. As a result of BST powder SEM, fine grain powder was clearly formed as both conditions (before and after mesh-sieving). BST powder was crystalline and non-cracking morphology.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to acknowledge our deep gratitude to Professor Dr Khin Mar Kyu, Head of Department of Physics, Dagon University and Professor Dr May Myint Si, Department of Physics, Dagon University, for allowing and encouraging us to present this paper.

References

- Ahmad, T. *et al.* (2005). *J. Mater. Res.*, **20**(6), 1415
- Goresy, E. *et al.* (2001). *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, **192**, 485
- Htet Htet Nwe *et al.* (2010). "Characterization of Calcium modified Lead Titanate Thin Film by Electrophoretic Method", *Proceedings of the Second International Conference on Science and Engineering*, **1**, 613
- Htet Htet Nwe *et al.* (2012) "Non-Volatile Memory Behaviour of MFIS Structure with Ba_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}TiO₃ Films for Memory Capacitor Application", *Advanced Material Research*, **557-559**, 1861-1864
- Lance, G. P. *et al.* (2000), *Journal of Dairy Science*, **80**(11), 2726
- Xing, X. *et al.* (2004). *J Alloys & Compounds*, **384**, 312

Online Material

<http://www.webelements.com/webelements/compounds/text/Ba/Ba1O1-1304285.html>